

EXPERIENCE, AFFECTS, AND ENABLING SPACES FOR SOCIAL INTERACTIONS: ESSAY ON THE APPROACH TO MENTAL HEALTH AND UNIVERSITY EXTENSION FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF VYGOTSKY AND GONZÁLEZ REY

VIVÊNCIA, AFETOS E ESPAÇOS HABILITADORES ÀS INTERAÇÕES SOCIAIS: ENSAIANDO ABORDAGEM À SAÚDE MENTAL E EXTENSÃO UNIVERSITÁRIA NA PERSPECTIVA DE VYGOTSKY E GONZÁLEZ REY

EXPERIENCIA, AFECTOS Y ESPACIOS POSIBILITADORES DE INTERACCIONES SOCIALES: ENSAYANDO UNA APROXIMACIÓN A LA SALUD MENTAL Y LA EXTENSIÓN UNIVERSITARIA DESDE LA PERSPECTIVA DE VYGOTSKY Y GONZÁLEZ REY

Fabiana Pinto de Almeida BIZARRIA¹
e-mail: fabianabizarria@pucminas.br

Leonardo Victor de Sá PINHEIRO²
e-mail: leonardopinheiro@hotmail.com

Ana Cristine Mendes da SILVA³
e-mail: cristinemendes@ufpi.edu.br

Flávia Lorenne Sampaio BARBOSA⁴
e-mail: flsbarbosa@ufpi.edu.br

How to reference this paper:

BIZARRIA, Fabiana Pinto de Almeida; PINHEIRO, Leonardo Victor de Sá; SILVA, Ana Cristine Mendes da; BARBOSA, Flávia Lorenne Sampaio. Experience, affects, and enabling spaces for social interactions: essay on the approach to mental health and university extension from the perspective of Vygotsky and González Rey. **Plurais - Revista Multidisciplinar**, Salvador, v. 10, n. 00, e025021, 2025. e-ISSN: 2177-5060. DOI: 10.29378/plurais.v10i00.21590

| **Submitted:** 06/09/2024

| **Revisions required:** 05/06/2025

| **Approved:** 07/08/2025

| **Published:** 17/12/2025

¹ Pontifical Catholic University of Minas Gerais (PUC/MG), Belo Horizonte – Minas Gerais (MG) – Brazil. Professor at the School of Psychology, PUC Minas, and faculty member of the Graduate Program in Psychology. Collaborating Professor in the Graduate Program in Public Management at the Federal University of Piauí.

² Federal University of Piauí (UFPI), Amílcar Ferreira Sobral Campus, Floriano– Piauí (PI) – Brazil. Tenured Professor in the Undergraduate Program in Business Administration at UFPI and in the Professional Master's Programs in Public Administration (PROFIAP/UFPI) and Public Management (PPGP).

³ Federal University of Piauí (UFPI), Amílcar Ferreira Sobral Campus (UFPI), Floriano – Piauí (PI) – Brazil. Recipient of a Scientific Initiation Scholarship (PIBIC) funded by CNPq/UFPI. Member of the Research Center on Psychosociology, Work, and Socioenvironmental Studies (NUPYTES).

⁴ Federal University of Piauí (UFPI), Amílcar Ferreira Sobral Campus (UFPI), Floriano – Piauí (PI) – Brazil. Tenured faculty member of the Distance Education Undergraduate Program in Data Management Technology at UFPI, Open and Distance Education Center (CEAD). Faculty member of the Graduate Program in Public Management and the Professional Master's Program in Public Administration (PROFIAP), both at UFPI.

Editors: Prof. Dr. Célia Tanajura Machado
Prof. Dr. Kathia Marise Borges Sales
Prof. Dr. Rosângela da Luz Matos
Deputy Executive Editor: Prof. Dr. José Anderson Santos Cruz

ABSTRACT: The research aims to define, in the form of a theoretical essay, an approach to the mental health of university students, integrating university extension as a complementary component in the psycho-emotional development of students. Along the path to health creation, it establishes spaces that enable experiences, interactions, that enhance connections, sense of belonging, and protagonism, experiences in the university context, strengthening the role of language and emotions in the 'social context of the psyche'. For this, 28 articles on 'academic experience', 'academic bond', and 'academic experience' were analyzed, along with contributions from Vygotsky and González Rey. It is understood that enabling spaces affectionately foster meanings and senses that contribute to health. Therefore, institutional dynamics could focus efforts on offering opportunities for experiences, favorable to affective experiences, interactions, validation, and affirmation of the different ways of being and acting of university students, resulting in an inclusive university context.

KEYWORDS: Multidimensional. Sickness. Mental Disorder. Technology. Symbolic.

RESUMO: A pesquisa visa definir, em forma de ensaio teórico, uma abordagem à saúde mental de universitários, integrando a extensão universitária como componente complementar no desenvolvimento psicoemocional dos estudantes. No caminho da produção de saúde, afirmam-se espaços habilitadores para as vivências e interações que potencializem vínculos, senso de pertencimento e protagonismo, experiências no contexto universitário, avigorando a função da linguagem e das emoções quanto ao "contexto social da psique". Para isso, 28 artigos sobre "vivência acadêmica", "vínculo acadêmico" e "experiência acadêmica" foram analisados, somando-se contribuições de Vygotsky e González Rey. Depreende-se que espaços habilitadores favoreçam, afetivamente, significados e sentidos que contribuem para a saúde. Portanto, a dinâmica institucional poderia centrar esforços em oferecer oportunidades às experiências favoráveis, às vivências afetivas, interações, validação e afirmação das diferentes maneiras de ser e agir dos universitários, resultando em um contexto universitário inclusivo.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Multidimensional. Adoecimento. Transtorno Mental. Tecnologia. Simbólico.

RESUMEN: La investigación pretende definir, en forma de ensayo teórico, un abordaje de la salud mental de los estudiantes universitarios, integrando la extensión universitaria como componente complementario en el desarrollo psicoemocional de los estudiantes. En el camino de la producción de salud, se afirman espacios posibilitadores de vivencias e interacciones, potenciando vínculos, sentido de pertenencia y protagonismo, experiencias en el contexto universitario, potenciando la función del lenguaje y las emociones en función del 'contexto social del psiquismo'. Para ello, se analizaron 28 artículos sobre 'experiencia académica', 'vínculo académico' y 'vivencia académica', añadiendo aportaciones de Vygotsky y González Rey. Al parecer, los espacios propicios favorecen significados y sentidos afectivos que contribuyen a la salud. Por lo tanto, las dinámicas institucionales podrían centrar sus esfuerzos en ofrecer oportunidades de experiencias favorables a vivencias afectivas, interacciones, validación y afirmación de las diferentes formas de ser y actuar de los universitarios, dando como resultado un contexto universitario inclusivo.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Multidimensional. Enfermedad. Trastorno mental. Tecnología. Simbólico.

Introduction

A country's development is directly linked to the quality of its education system and to its capacity to train professionals capable of responding to social and technological demands that are transforming teaching–learning processes (Cechinel; Santos, 2020; Haugsbakk, 2020). In addition, the labor market increasingly requires competencies such as communication, teamwork, leadership, and creative thinking—the so-called soft skills (Lok; Cheng; Choong, 2020).

In Brazil, policies aimed at expanding access to higher education have increased not only enrollment but also the diversity of the student body in terms of social class, gender, and age (Suehiro; Andrade, 2018; Aragão; Alfinito; Luís, 2018). This new profile brings heterogeneous goals and expectations (Malequeta; Santos; Pery, 2017) and highlights problems already observed in international universities, such as high rates of failure and dropout concentrated in the first semesters (Cruz-Campos *et al.*, 2023).

Within this context, the mental health of university students has become a central concern. There is a “high prevalence of anxiety and depressive symptoms in this population when compared to the general population” (Silva *et al.*, 2023, p. 104, our translation). According to Awang and Noor (2023), these disorders contribute to dropout and generate significant social costs for students, institutions, and society.

The World Health Organization (2022) estimates that 14% of adolescents worldwide experience mental disorders. In the United States, a survey conducted by the Healthy Minds Network (2022–2023) with 76,406 university students identified prevalence rates of 41% for depression, 36% for anxiety, and 14% for suicidal ideation; the anxiety rate nearly doubled over six years (from 17% to 31%). Studies in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, France, Spain, Australia, and Nordic countries indicate that up to 73% of students face difficulties in maintaining psychological well-being.

In Brazil, the National Survey on the Socioeconomic and Cultural Profile of Undergraduate Students at Federal Higher Education Institutions reported that 83.5% of university students experience emotional difficulties; 60% report symptoms of anxiety, and suicidal ideation increased from 6.1% to 8.5% (Andifes, 2019). Brito *et al.* (2021) further note that self-harm and suicide are already the third leading cause of death among adolescents.

These indicators gain particular relevance when considering the transitions typical of university life, marked by changes that require rapid adaptation and may foster psychological distress and dropout (Malequeta; Santos; Pery, 2017). During this period, young people

consolidate identities and make decisions that generate new priorities, insecurities, and potential frustrations—factors that can compromise academic performance (Lima *et al.*, 2023; Suehiro; Andrade, 2018). However, much of the research on mental health remains anchored in an individualizing biomedical perspective that inadequately engages with the complexity of well-being (Lima *et al.*, 2023).

Weak family ties, financial challenges, and the need to balance study and work may lead to exhaustion and hinder learning (Lima *et al.*, 2023). Evidence shows that retention, academic success, and student satisfaction depend on social, economic, cultural, and institutional factors (Nhantumbo; Carreño; Bruce-Nhantumbo, 2018; Suehiro; Andrade, 2018).

From the perspective of University Social Responsibility (Chen; Nasongkhla; Donaldson, 2015), Higher Education Institutions are called upon to invest in the promotion of student mental health. Research indicates that interventions focused on managing academic life—such as study organization, leisure, and interpersonal relationships—as well as programs centered on socioemotional support, self-knowledge, self-esteem, and stress management, contribute to a healthier university experience (Ariño; Bardagi, 2018; Silva *et al.*, 2023).

Along this path, university outreach activities also play a fundamental role in building connections between society and the academic community, while providing meaningful professional and university experiences (Oliveira *et al.*, 2019). For Ribeiro, Ponte, and Silva (2017), outreach is indispensable to the formative foundation of both students and professionals, despite the challenges of consolidating it alongside research and teaching. Thus, Higher Education Institutions should address emerging demands and the emotional–affective dynamics involved in the transitions experienced by university students.

This theoretical essay presents an approach to university mental health that incorporates outreach as a complementary component of students’ psychoemotional development. In this model, health promotion requires the creation of enabling spaces capable of fostering experiences, interactions, bonds, a sense of belonging, and agency in everyday academic life, reinforcing the role of language and emotions in the so-called “social context of the psyche.” This perspective shifts the focus from illness to the production of health, in line with Ariño and Bardagi (2018), Bandura (2005), Chariyeva *et al.* (2013), and Rodrigues *et al.* (2023).

The notion of enabling spaces resonates with the contributions of Lev S. Vygotsky and Fernando L. González Rey. For these authors, environments that promote symbolic encounters and outreach actions intertwine language, emotions, meanings, and senses in the constitution of subjectivity. Experience is thus understood as the unit of the social situation of development:

the affective–cognitive relationship between the individual and the environment, inseparable from the intersubjective interactions that sustain it (González Rey, 2000).

Methodology

This study adopts the methodological perspective of the theoretical essay, characterized by critical and argumentative analysis of the theme of enabling spaces. The writing is structured as a reflective and experimental process, supported by a literature review and by an essayistic stance that, according to Larrosa (2004), is constructed as thought in motion, seeking not absolute truths but an open and critical exploration of meanings.

According to Adorno (2003), the essay does not submit to the rigid conventions of science, as its purpose is to examine ideas freely, articulating readings and arguments around a specific theme. From this perspective, Botton (2011) emphasizes that the essay operates simultaneously within and beyond conceptual thought: although grounded in theoretical reflection, it breaks with the systematic logic of science by preserving the tension between concept and object—a tension that both dogma and scientific method tend to suppress.

Moreover, Botton (2011) understands the essay as valuing experience as an inseparable part of the process of understanding, rather than merely as a means of analysis. This approach materializes in a deliberately unfinished text that functions as an exercise in reflection, exploring alternative approaches to a specific problem.

In the field of health, studies such as those by Moreira (2019) and Roso and Romanini (2014) exemplify the methodological use of the essay as a strategy for argumentative construction. These works adopt an exploratory stance and employ conceptual mapping as a tool for critically reflecting on the topics addressed, fostering open dialogue with other researchers.

Following this logic, a bibliographic survey on the topic of “university student mental health” was conducted on November 28, 2023, using the CAPES Journals Platform, with expanded access to all its databases through an institutional affiliation with a graduate program. Study selection considered recurring concepts in the literature, such as bonds, experience, and satisfaction with the academic experience. The notion of self-efficacy emerged transversally across discussions, motivating an expansion of readings around this concept.

The bibliographic search was conducted using the descriptor “academic bonding,” covering all document types, languages, and time periods available on the CAPES Journals Platform. The selection was limited to the period from 2018 to 2023, with a filter for peer-reviewed articles. Based on these criteria, 12 studies were identified, of which 2 were excluded due to duplication, resulting in 10 selected articles. Applying the same criteria to the descriptor “academic experience” yielded 13 articles, with 2 duplicates removed, totaling 11 studies. Subsequently, the combination of the terms “academic experience” and “satisfaction” using the Boolean operator AND produced 18 results; 11 were excluded due to duplication, leaving 7 articles⁵.

Considering the thematic intersections with university student mental health, as argued throughout the essay, the final corpus comprised 28 articles selected for reading and analysis. The writing of the essay was guided by an articulation of the conceptions discussed in these studies, seeking a coherent and comprehensible presentation, as proposed by Botton (2011) in the essayistic approach and by Torracco (2016) from the perspective of integrative review. The structure of the study follows three main movements: it begins with an integrative overview of the analyzed texts; then incorporates the theoretical contributions of Vygotsky and González Rey; and, finally, presents suggestions for practical contributions related to the theme.

Bonds, Experience, and Satisfaction with the Academic Experience – An Integrative Perspective

To initiate the integration of the texts, the analysis departs from the shift in emphasis from illness to health, as proposed by Bandura (2005), Gueroni *et al.* (2024), Rodrigues *et al.* (2023), and Lima *et al.* (2023), with the aim of fostering less fragmented, individualizing, and pathologizing approaches that are institutionally disconnected. In this sense, research contributions on university students’ mental health highlight the relevance of lived experiences, bonds, and satisfaction with academic experiences, including a sense of self-efficacy, as well

⁵ The selected studies are: Santos, Zanon and Ilha (2019), Pereira-Neto, Faria and Almeida (2022), Albuquerque *et al.* (2019), Campira, Bulaque and Almeida (2021), Aragão, Alfinito and Correia (2018), Oliveira *et al.* (2020), Suehiro and Andrade (2018), Alonso, Alonso and Fernández (2020), Campesino (2023), Valdivia (2019), Guanin-Fajardo and Barranquero (2022), Taschetto and Rosa (2019), Trejo *et al.* (2019), Fleisner *et al.* (2023), Roque *et al.* (2018), Mérida-López, Quintana-Orts and Extremera (2022), Peris Blat (2019), Garcia and Pan (2023), Rodrigues *et al.* (2023), Nascimento and Ferraz (2021), Cechinel and Santos (2020), Medeiros and Gonçalves (2018), Santos *et al.* (2018), Siqueira *et al.* (2020), Arakawa-Belaunde *et al.* (2018), Fadel *et al.* (2018), Guzmán-Utreras, Baeza-Ugarte and Morales-Navarro (2023), Nina and Cruz de Oliveira (2019).

as interdisciplinary approaches and intersectoral interventions related to the everyday production of life–health, recognizing the primacy of health promotion.

Lived experiences, bonds, and satisfaction with experiences, as they relate to the intellectual, affective, and social dimensions (Coulon, 2017; Garcia; Pan, 2023), offer interpretations of “personal–individual” aspects, understood as perceptions of physical and psychological well-being associated with balance and affective stability, optimism in decision-making, and self-confidence. These factors represent decisive elements for persistence in higher education. Soares *et al.* (2018) further emphasize that expectations regarding the university can increase levels of satisfaction, thereby strengthening academic bonding and connection to the degree program. In this regard, it is important to note that outreach activities, for example, also enhance the quality of university experiences, as they contribute to the development of both students’ professional and personal knowledge (Siveres, 2012).

Within this context, academic experience emerges as a fundamental and central element for bonds and satisfaction with experiences. Garcia and Pan (2023) explain that the “interpersonal” dimension, associated with self-perceived competence to establish and maintain social relationships, motivates students to seek help. Additionally, the “vocational/career” dimension provides meaning to feelings related to professional and formative development, contributing to feeling competent and satisfied with the degree program. The “study” dimension, in turn, encompasses everyday academic life in response to activity-related demands, involving, for example, time management, the establishment of routines, and study planning.

Drawing on the contributions of Santos, Zanon, and Ilha (2019), academic experience is understood as incorporating everyday social practices in which students, through interaction, organize feelings and meanings, attributing sense to their experiences. In this context, Oliveira *et al.* (2019) argue that university outreach expands the boundaries of academic experiences, as such activities enrich students’ education by aligning it with the real needs of future professionals and by fostering the development of skills and competencies.

It follows, therefore, that the quality of these experiences shapes not only students’ evaluations, which result in satisfaction, but, above all, the development of self-efficacy, when ways of being and acting are validated through interactive processes within academic experiences. This characterizes an inclusive social and cultural context that is favorable to cooperation and diversity. Along this path, persistence, adaptation, and inclusion are associated

with less stressful and less anxiety-provoking experiences, as emphasized by Guzmán-Utreras, Baeza-Ugarte, and Morales-Navarro (2023).

Santos, Zanon, and Ilha (2019, p. 4) argue that, as a development of self-efficacy—a concept grounded in Bandura’s (2005) social cognitive theory—behaviors such as solidarity and cooperation among peers, the formation of friendships to share difficulties, the lending of materials, and participation in group activities, such as studying and presentations, are fundamental to promoting academic satisfaction.

In this context, action-related self-efficacy beliefs involve the willingness to act in the face of challenges when students perceive themselves as capable of addressing them. Moreover, developing and maintaining social interactions, according to Santos, Zanon, and Ilha (2019), are the self-efficacy beliefs that most strongly contribute to satisfaction with academic experiences. For Chariyeva *et al.* (2013), self-efficacy constitutes a protective factor that contributes to students’ health and well-being, underscoring its relevance for achieving personal and academic goals.

Thus, valuing peer relationships, fostering interaction among students, and building collaborative networks are aspects that can contribute to emotional well-being, the construction of a welcoming environment, and mental health in the university setting (Campesino, 2023; Valdivia, 2019). These processes promote an expanded sense of belonging and academic identity, which are crucial elements for strengthening academic bonds (Campesino, 2023; Dogan, 2015; Valdivia, 2019). To this end, “formative spaces–times must be understood in a complex manner, in which plural and heterogeneous forms of knowledge intertwine and engage in dialogue amid tensions, negotiations of meaning, and the production of significance” (Ribeiro; Pontes; Silva, 2017, p. 63, our translation).

However, although the construction of academic bonds may begin even before entry into university—when cognitive foundations and previously developed competencies act as pillars for subsequent adaptation and academic performance (Alonso, Alonso, & Fernández, 2020)—studies on academic bonding, such as those by Alves and Honório (2013), Kramer (2003), Kramer and Faria (2007), and Ariño and Bardagi (2018), emphasize that the establishment of bonds is influenced by students’ capacity for socialization, particularly through support networks that contribute to addressing academic challenges.

Institutional social practices centered on the relevance of social interactions for university mental health can be derived from studies on “academic experiences,” such as those by Almeida and Ferreira (1997), Almeida, Ferreira, and Soares (1999), Almeida, Soares, and

Ferreira (2003), and Granado *et al.* (2005). Based on these studies, it is possible to recognize the importance of ensuring physical and psychological well-being, emotional balance, affective stability, optimism, and self-confidence, fostered through peer relationships that, when cooperative and inclusive, lead to self-perceived social skills in bond formation and in seeking help related to studies, time management, and the use of available institutional resources. The provision of knowledge and support related to degree programs and careers is also emphasized, as it contributes to students' future projects connected to their chosen professions.

Within this context, experiential activities developed through university outreach play an essential role by enabling a formative movement that fosters dialogue with plural forms of knowledge, grounded in experiences and reflections lived across diverse sociocultural environments, thereby generating varied and plural meanings (Ribeiro; Pontes; Silva, 2017).

Accordingly, satisfaction with academic experiences—which reflects students' appraisal of their educational experiences, as defined by Schleich, Polydoro, and Santos (2006) and Soares, Vasconcelos, and Almeida (2002)—is linked to the quality of interactions that lead university students to positively evaluate formative experiences, teaching quality, relationships with faculty and peers, the curriculum, administration, pedagogical resources, and facilities (Fadel *et al.*, 2018). This perception is fundamental to student engagement throughout the educational trajectory, as indicated by Aragão, Alfinito, and Luís (2018), Oliveira *et al.* (2020), and Santos, Severo, and Correia (2022).

Regarding the commitment of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to this issue, Oliveira *et al.* (2020, p. 10) acknowledge that universities “need to develop actions that foster a stronger sense of belonging among students with respect to their choices, aiming to achieve higher levels of satisfaction.” Moreover, student satisfaction is associated with institutional reputation, image, and credibility—factors that cultivate trust in the structural, administrative, and pedagogical dimensions of higher education—underscoring the importance of practical, academic, and personal support for an effective student–institution connection (Santos; Romeiro, 2017; Ngueyn; Leblanc, 2001; Pereira; Gil, 2007; Tontini; Walter, 2011; Zevallos; Washbur, 2014). Along this path, managing the typical challenges of university life, according to Ariño and Bardagi (2018), contributes to mental health and prompts reflections, such as those proposed by Gueroni *et al.* (2024), regarding the provision of health promotion programs, including the strengthening of self-efficacy.

For Mérida-López, Extremera, and Quintana-Orts (2023), the diversity of experiences that promote inclusion is fundamental to mitigating academic burnout and fostering student

success and the strengthening of bonds. Additionally, students' experiences within the academic environment can encourage participation and leadership, promoting democratic principles of equity and shared decision-making—elements that are essential to the construction of graduates' institutional identity, as explained by Queiroz and Paula (2017) and Dollinger and Vanderlelie (2019).

Drawing on the work of Nascimento and Ferraz (2021), it is therefore argued that social interactions are fundamental to university mental health. In this direction, attention is directed to understanding the quality of these interactions, particularly as ongoing social, cultural, and economic dynamics challenge social relations—especially those shaped by individualistic and competitive logics that activate hierarchies of power, contributing to spaces that classify and exclude individuals according to dominant norms. When social interactions fail to enable inclusive and cooperative dynamics, academic experiences of isolation, helplessness, and low self-esteem in relation to academic challenges may arise, triggering suffering, anxiety and depression, disappointment, and frustration, ultimately leading to withdrawal or dropout.

Therefore, Cechinel and Santos (2020) suggest that “social interaction” is the most relevant aspect of academic experience. Institutional welcoming as an academic experience—also embedded in social and institutional interaction—is addressed by Garcia and Pan (2023, p. 6, our translation), who argue that “academic experience must be analyzed in relation to the quality of formative practices and student assistance and welcoming policies.” Cechinel and Santos (2020) also draw attention to the “time” dimension, as university students seek to maximize and accelerate activities inherent to undergraduate education.

From this perspective, institutional welcoming should provide opportunities for building bonds that are conducive to coping with the challenges of academic life, as noted by Medeiros and Gonçalves (2018), while placing particular emphasis on empowering those involved. In accelerated dynamics, this constitutes an additional challenge to the quality of formative practices and student assistance policies.

Experience, affect, and enabling spaces for social interactions: contributions from Vygotsky and González Rey

Associated with discussions on the increasing prevalence of mental health-related distress among university students, as indicated by data from the World Health Organization (2022) and Andifes (2019), the quality of interactions is identified as a key factor in mental health. To understand what constitutes “quality,” the contributions of Vygotsky and González Rey are mobilized, based on the understanding that *experience* represents the unit of the social situation of development, in which emotions, meanings, and senses intertwine in the constitution of subjectivity. Within this framework, enabling spaces are understood as psychosocial constructions capable of mobilizing meaningful social interactions and contributing to students’ emotional well-being.

Along this path, if evaluation processes are viewed as having little relevance for social action, they may generate broader conflicts within social interaction policies. However, by listening to the protagonists of outreach actions, the academic environment not only reassesses itself but also expands, incorporating the reflections and perspectives of those outside academia and thus overcoming traditional boundaries (Ribeiro; Pontes; Silva, 2017). According to these authors, evaluative methods in university outreach should encompass both the academic community and the social agents involved, as both are essential actors capable of promoting concrete changes in the environment.

González Rey (2008), from a historical-cultural perspective inspired by Vygotsky, defines subjective meaning as a symbolic–emotional process organized within the individual’s social experience. Emotions and symbolic expressions not only coexist but are intertwined through interactions and reinterpretations that situate everyday lived experience, such as:

[...] complex subjective configurations of the lived, which represent subjective productions [...] lived experience is inseparable from the subjective configuration of the one who lives it [...] and characterizes the differentiated relations that occur across the different spaces of the subject’s social life (González Rey, 2008, p. 234, our translation).

Inspired by González Rey (2008), this perspective recognizes the complex network of subjective meanings and expressions that emerges from the interaction between individuals and the university social context. Enabling spaces for meaningful experiences operate in singular ways, as shared meanings and social interactions are uniquely organized, exerting differentiated influences on subjectivity and mental health.

Studies on “university student mental health” attest to the influence of bonds (Meng; Zhang, 2023; Dogan, 2015). Thus, from a Vygotskian analysis, “academic success” can be understood as a result of the quality of interactions and bonds established within the university environment—from entry into higher education (Alonso; Alonso; Fernández, 2020) to the pedagogical methodologies adopted (Mérida-López; Extremera; Quintana-Orts, 2023)—promoting perceptions of support and integration and activating motives for students to pursue their goals. In this way, academic bonds, activated within enabling spaces, can mobilize meanings related to social support, resulting in experiences that are favorable to emotional and cognitive development.

Interactive processes in spaces that enable cooperation, welcoming, and recognition of potential can, in turn, contribute to perceptions of self-efficacy, or to beliefs in one’s own capacity to overcome challenges (Lacerda; Yunes; Valentini, 2022). In other words, this entails empowerment with social inclusion, attentive to differences and student agency, since rethinking the inclusion/exclusion relationship “represents a recovery of individual and collective dimensions, not homogenized by prevailing culture, but reframed in the search for social representations, singularities, meanings and significations, and therefore the subjective character of lived relationships” (Gomes; Gonzalez Rey, 2007, p. 408, our translation).

Along this path, subjective meaning—proposed by González Rey (2008) as a symbolic–emotional unit that emerges within the individual’s social experience—thus offers an approach to university mental health, insofar as:

[...] subjective meanings represent the psychological units that characterize the way lived experience is subjectivized—experience not in what it objectively means to an external observer, but in its full emotional and symbolic charge for the person who lives it (Gomes; Gonzalez Rey, 2007, p. 409, our translation).

Therefore, university experiences that embody interactive dynamics, when situated in spaces that enable emotional expression, enhance the meanings and senses attributed to the academic trajectory, symbolizing experiences oriented toward the everyday production of health. This leads to reflection on how educational institutions can better configure their practices to mobilize interpersonal relationships that take into account subjectivity—“understood as the production of meanings, [which] elevates the individual and their entire history to a new position, now endowed with senses, meanings, and emotionality” (Gomes; Gonzalez Rey, 2007, p. 409, our translation).

In this way, the critical analysis of this theoretical and empirical exchange reinforces the premise that building an inclusive and empathetic academic community is fundamental to advancing university mental health. In this regard, Machado, Facci, and Barroco (2011, p. 650, our translation) note that, for Vygotsky, feelings and emotions are socially and historically grounded, with emotion and cognition being interdependent in the psychological process, acknowledging “the active participation of emotional life in the cognitive sphere of thought and in the creative movement, which is imagination.”

Against this backdrop, revisiting the studies surveyed in this research suggests that the “institutional” dimension should assume a central role—from references to university social responsibility to social commitment, as articulated by Martín-Baró (1997)—as evidenced in the studies by Pereira-Neto, Faria, and Almeida (2022), Albuquerque *et al.* (2019), Suehiro and Andrade (2018), Aragão, Alfinito, and Luís (2018), and Campira, Bulaque, and Almeida (2021).

Garcia and Pan (2023), Meng and Zhang (2023), Dogan (2015), Alonso, Alonso, and Fernández (2020), Valdivia (2019), and Mérida-López, Extremera, and Quintana-Orts (2023) offer even more emphatic contributions by asserting that higher education institutions must rethink their practices, policies, and cultures when addressing the issue of university student mental health. Emphasizing the construction of spaces that promote meaningful social interaction and emotional and cognitive development—while considering the complex tapestry of subjectivities students bring to these interactions—is therefore essential to creating an academic environment that not only supports academic success but also fosters psychological flourishing.

Along this path, Vygotsky (1995) highlighted the importance of the social environment in cognitive and emotional development, proposing that learning is intrinsically a social phenomenon, just as González Rey (2008) emphasized the role of subjectivity and subjective meanings constructed in social interactions and their profound influence on individual and collective experience.

By fostering a sense of community and belonging, such spaces are crucial to mental health, as feelings of isolation can be a significant source of stress and anxiety among university students. According to Baumeister and Leary (1995), the need to belong is a fundamental driving force in human interactions and is directly related to emotional well-being. Promoting student agency within university spaces means valuing students’ voices, perspectives, and

contributions. This not only strengthens self-efficacy but also contributes to the development of critical and creative skills.

In this respect, Vygotsky's (1989) sociocultural activity theory suggests that human development is deeply influenced by participation in cultural activities and by the internalization of social practices. Therefore, spaces that encourage student agency—allowing students to actively engage in projects, research, and community initiatives—are essential for robust mental health.

Accordingly, the role of public managers in the planning, design, and implementation of public policies that promote student agency through university outreach is of paramount importance. This movement seeks to develop in students a reflective, critical, and interactive professional profile (Arrais; Ferreira; Antunes, 2021). Student agency in university outreach thus promotes an active stance, enabling students to play a central role in project development rather than acting merely as implementers (Arrais; Ferreira; Antunes, 2021).

This study emphasizes the importance of language as a mediator in social relations and in the construction of meanings, in line with Vygotsky's view of language as a primary instrument of cultural and cognitive mediation. In the university context, prioritizing spaces that elevate language and communication enables rich exchanges of experiences, emotions, and knowledge, thereby enhancing the educational experience.

Moreover, the valuing of emotions, as advocated by González Rey, emerges as a crucial aspect of personal development and learning, unfolding within the dynamics of social interactions. The creation of academic environments that promote collaboration, dialogue, and active participation is decisive for an integral approach to university mental health—one that seeks not only academic success but also students' well-being and self-realization. This perspective challenges higher education institutions to reformulate their practices and infrastructures in order to develop an academic community that sustains both academic performance and emotional and social support, thereby proposing a new definition of university mental health: not merely the absence of disorders, but the creation of an ecosystem that fosters holistic growth and human development.

The university is a social microcosm that shares power dynamics, hierarchies, and cultural norms. Consequently, its spaces may hinder meaningful experiences when social interactions are not welcoming of the subjective singularities of students who bring diverse trajectories to the university, including experiences of social exclusion. Defining spaces that enable healthy interactions therefore requires acknowledging that intersubjective encounters

may be traversed by competitive logics, domination, and even subordination of differences—especially affecting those at the margins of society.

Thus, a critical analysis of these spaces must also encompass the institutional structures and practices that organize them, including educational policies, curricula, teaching and assessment methods, and the organizational culture of higher education institutions. For this reason, when focusing on subjectivity and social representations in the university context, caution is required to avoid reifying the university experience by assuming uniformity, which underlies exclusionary criteria that disregard the diversity of ways of being and existing within the academic community.

Final Considerations

The essayistic movement represents an approximation and a reflection. The discussion developed in this study seeks to integratively revisit conceptions explored in the field of university mental health, contributing to dialogues on outreach within the academic context that emerge from research on spaces enabling social interactions. Aware of the challenges inherent in this approach, the essay is also presented as an invitation to alternative ways of understanding the phenomenon, with the aim of fostering change, since “there is no true knowledge that is not essentially linked to transformative knowledge of reality, just as there is no transformative knowledge of reality that does not involve a change in relationships among human beings” (Martín-Baró, 1997, p. 27, our translation)⁶.

This involves recognizing the urgency of enabling spaces for symbolic encounters, situating the relevance of language and emotions in light of the social character of the psyche—spaces that enable the active participation of emotional life, enhancing cognition, thought, and creativity among university students, and contributing to health promotion, insofar as experiences mobilize shared meanings and senses attributed to lived experiences.

As the psychosocial construction of these experiences occurs at the level of interactions—that is, from an intersubjective perspective—studies in the field of “bonds” support the main aspect to be emphasized within academic experiences: symbolic social interactions. Consequently, it is essential to expand the scope and quality of outreach activities,

⁶ The reference to Martín-Baró does not seek to circumscribe mental health to psychology. Recognizing it in everyday health care and its multidimensionality, health promotion is assumed through the interdisciplinary and interprofessional social dimension, where the know-how of psychology is organized with other knowledge, in systematic and intersectoral agendas.

aiming at the resignification and systematization of actions undertaken (Ribeiro; Pontes; Silva, 2017).

If lived experiences foster integration, adaptation, and the capacity to address daily challenges, they may also affectively promote meanings associated with spaces of welcome, interaction, validation, recognition, and the affirmation of differences. Such processes contribute to developments in self-confidence related to the establishment of bonds and the resolution of challenges, thereby favoring perceptions of satisfaction with the academic trajectory.

The quality of interactions, therefore, represents a central factor in university students' mental health, particularly within an institutional context that offers spaces enabling inclusion and cooperation, as well as opportunities for lived experiences and academic engagement. Through university outreach, these experiences foster integration, adaptation, and the resolution of daily challenges, which may lead to perceptions of the educational trajectory that do not generate suffering.

University social responsibility must thus be understood as a commitment to social transformation that challenges exclusionary norms and promotes social justice and equity. Addressing the challenges associated with university students' mental health is therefore not merely a matter of educational policy, but a social and moral imperative that reflects higher education institutions' commitment to the future of society.

These experiences, supported by learning contexts, enhance self-efficacy and mental health, underscoring the importance of considering both shared meanings (curricular content) and the personal senses attributed by each student to their academic experiences. It thus becomes evident that the construction of senses and meanings in the university context is a complex and multifaceted process, requiring an integrative approach that is sensitive to social, cultural, and institutional dynamics. In this context, promoting mental health involves valuing students' lived experiences, strengthening community bonds, and creating an academic outreach environment that is simultaneously challenging and supportive, capable of nurturing both personal and collective development.

By adopting this proposition within the horizon of psychology's social commitment, for example, the essay seeks not only to address the reference issue—university students' mental health—but, above all, to advocate for the promotion of mental health as an extension-based form of university social responsibility, embedded in programmatic, formative, and organizational agendas. In this way, the aim is to provide higher education students with a

healthy, welcoming, and satisfying environment that recognizes singular identity trajectories and the diverse ways of being, acting, thinking, and interacting socially.

The discussion advanced in this theoretical essay, grounded in the contributions of Vygotsky and González Rey, offers a series of promising reflections. Nevertheless, like any theoretical investigation, it faces inherent limitations that outline paths for future research, such as the complexity of subjectivity and the lack of engagement with reinterpretations of other works by Vygotsky and González Rey.

For future studies, understanding dynamics related to “enabling spaces” for university students may generate developments that are favorable to institutional propositions and to programmatic and formative agendas focused on health promotion in the university context. Moreover, developing methodologies and analyzing outreach-based interventions aimed at promoting enabling spaces for university students’ mental health may also provide relevant contributions to the field.

In defining spaces that enable high-quality interactions, it can therefore be inferred, as a final reflection, that validating ways of being and acting within an inclusive scenario may contribute to individuals’ self-perception of their own capacities to face everyday challenges—an issue that becomes more complex given the technological dimension now present in spaces of interaction. Future research may broaden the debate on the challenges posed by virtualized relationships, considering their varied meanings for “enabling spaces” as a way of problematizing university students’ mental health. Finally, recognizing that the diversity of academic experiences and the acknowledgment of multiple identity trajectories are shaped by social classifications such as gender and race expands understanding of how enabling spaces may be experienced and endowed with meaning, thereby also calling for further investigation.

REFERENCES

- ADORNO, Theodor W. **Notas de literatura I**. Tradução e apresentação de Jorge M. B. de Almeida. São Paulo: Duas Cidades; Editora 34, 2003. 176 p.
- ALBUQUERQUE, L. G. M. *et al.* Satisfação com a experiência acadêmica entre estudantes de medicina. **Revista de Educação em Saúde**, v. 7, n. 2, p. 101–110, 2019. DOI: 10.29237/2358-9868.2019v7i2.p99-108.
- ALMEIDA, L. S.; FERREIRA, J. A. G.; SOARES, A. P. **Questionário de Vivências Acadêmicas**: construção e validação de uma versão reduzida (QVA-r). 1999.
- ALMEIDA, L. S.; FERREIRA, J. A. G.; SOARES, A. P. **Questionário de Vivências Acadêmicas (QVA e QVA-r)**. 2003.
- ALMEIDA, L. S.; FERREIRA, J. A. **Questionário de Vivência Acadêmica**. Braga: Universidade do Minho, 1997.
- ALMEIDA, L. S.; SOARES, A. P.; FERREIRA, J. A. Questionário de vivências acadêmicas (QVA e QVA-R). In: GONÇALVES, M. M. *et al.* (org.). **Avaliação psicológica: instrumentos validados para a população portuguesa**. Coimbra: Quarteto Editora, 2003. p. 113–130.
- ALONSO, J. A. V.; ALONSO, M. J. B.; FERNÁNDEZ, R. L. El éxito académico en el primer año de la carrera de ingeniería industrial y su vínculo con factores académicos previos. **Páginas de Educación**, v. 13, n. 1, p. 42–57, 2020.
- ALVES, J. D.; HONÓRIO, L. C. Vínculos entre alunos e uma instituição de ensino superior: desenvolvimento e proposição de uma escala de medida. **GESTÃO.Org**, v. 11, n. 2, p. 391–427, 2013. DOI: 10.51359/1679-1827.2013.21733.
- ANDIFES. **V Pesquisa Nacional de Perfil Socioeconômico e Cultural dos(as) Graduandos(as) das IFES**. Brasília, 2019.
- ARAGÃO, B. S.; ALFINITO, S.; LUÍS, C. J. Satisfação com a experiência acadêmica de estudantes do ensino superior. **Consumer Behavior Review**, v. 2, n. 2, p. 96–107, 2018. DOI: 10.21714/2526-78842018v2n2p96-107.
- ARAKAWA-BELAUNDE, A. *et al.* Vivências acadêmicas e ações de promoção da saúde em uma instituição de longa permanência para idosos: relato de experiência fonoaudiológica. **Distúrbios da Comunicação**, v. 30, n. 2, p. 385–391, 2018. DOI: 10.23925/2176-2724.2018v30i2p-385-391.
- ARIÑO, D. O.; BARDAGI, M. P. Relação entre fatores acadêmicos e saúde mental de estudantes universitários. **Psicologia em Pesquisa**, v. 12, n. 3, p. 44–52, 2018. DOI: 10.24879/2018001200300544.
- ARRAIS, E. L.; FERREIRA, J. M.; ANTUNES, J. O. O protagonismo estudantil na extensão universitária: a experiência do Núcleo de Atualização Pública na Universidade Federal do Cariri. **Revista Conexão UEPG**, v. 17, n. 1, p. 1–12, 2021. DOI: 10.5212/Rev.Conexao.v.17.16859.009.

AWANG, Z. L.; NOOR, M. F. M. Factors influencing dropout students in higher education. **Education Research International**, 2023.

BANDURA, A. The primacy of self-regulation in health promotion. **Applied Psychology: An International Review**, v. 54, n. 2, p. 245–254, 2005. DOI: 10.1111/j.1464-0597.2005.00208.x.

BAUMEISTER, R. F.; LEARY, M. R. The need to belong: desire for interpersonal attachments as a fundamental human motivation. **Psychological Bulletin**, v. 117, n. 3, p. 497–529, 1995. DOI: 10.1037/0033-2909.117.3.497.

BOTTON, A. M. Notas sobre o ensaio em Theodor W. Adorno. **Graphos**, João Pessoa, v. 13, n. 1, 2011.

BRITO, F. A. M. de *et al.* Violência autoprovocada em adolescentes no Brasil, segundo os meios utilizados. **Cogitare Enfermagem**, 2021.

CAMPESINO, A. R. Una isla con mar: vínculos académico-culturales entre Paraguay y España en el siglo XXI. **El Nacional**, 29 oct. 2023. Available at: <https://elnacional.com.py/cultura/una-isla-con-mar-vinculos-academico-culturales-paraguay-espana-siglo-xxi-n56455>. Accessed in: 15 Jan. 2025.

CAMPIRA, F. P.; BULAQUE, P. Z.; ALMEIDA, L. S. Satisfação com experiências acadêmicas: variáveis preditoras em estudantes universitários de Moçambique. **Revista Ibero-Americana de Estudos em Educação**, Araraquara, v. 16, n. 3, p. 1979–1994, 2021. DOI: 10.21723/riaee.v16i3.15421.

CECHINEL, E.; SANTOS, A. R. Experiências memoráveis na vivência acadêmica em cursos de administração: um estudo à luz das experiências em serviços. **Revista Gestão Universitária na América Latina**, v. 13, n. 1, p. 137–158, 2020. DOI: 10.5007/1983-4535.2020v13n1p137.

CHARIYEVA, Z. *et al.* The role of self-efficacy and motivation to explain the effect of motivational interviewing time on changes in risky sexual behavior among people living with HIV: a mediation analysis. **AIDS and Behavior**, v. 17, p. 813–823, 2013. DOI: 10.1007/s10461-011-0115-8.

CHEN, S.-H.; NASONGKHLA, J.; DONALDSON, J. A. University social responsibility (USR): identifying an ethical foundation within higher education institutions. **The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology**, v. 14, n. 4, p. 165, 2015.

COULON, A. O ofício de estudante: a entrada na vida universitária. **Educação e Pesquisa**, v. 43, p. 1239–1250, 2017. DOI: 10.1590/s1517-9702201710167954.

CRUZ-CAMPOS, J. C. D.; VICTORIA-MALDONADO, J. J.; MARTÍNEZ-DOMINGO, J.; CAMPOS-SOTO, M. N. Causes of academic dropout in higher education in Andalusia and proposals for its prevention at university: A systematic review. **Frontiers in Education**, v. 8, p. 01-13. 2023. DOI: 10.3389/feduc.2023.1130952.

DE OLIVEIRA, E. S.; SILVÉRIO, C. E.; FLORES, R. P.; FELDKIRCHER, J. M.; NUNES, M. M.; OKUBO, R. Programa de extensão “Fisioterapia esportiva”: Uma vivência

extensionista. **Revista Conexão UEPG**, v. 15, n. 3, p. 269-273, 2019. DOI: 10.5212/Rev.Conexao.v.15.i3.0006.

DOGAN, U. Envolvimento dos alunos, autoeficácia acadêmica e motivação acadêmica como preditores de desempenho acadêmico. **O Antropólogo**, v. 20, n. 3, p. 553-561, 2015.

DOLLINGER, M.; VANDERLELIE, J. Developing and enacting student governance and leadership training in higher education. A Practice Report. **Student Success**, v. 10, n. 2. p. 59-64, 2019. DOI: 10.5204/ssj.v10i2.1309.

FADEL, C. B.; SOUZA, J. A. D.; BORDIN, D.; GARBIN, C. A. S.; GARBIN, A. J. Í.; SALIBA, N. A. Satisfaction with the academic experience among graduate students of a brazilian public university. **RGO-Revista Gaúcha de Odontologia**, v. 66, p. 50-59, 2018.

FLEISNER, P.; LUCERO, G.; GALAZZI, L.; BILLI, N. La teoría de Haraway del conocimiento situado y su vínculo con la ontología relacional de Barad y el análisis de prácticas académicas en Stengers y Despret. **Nuevo Itinerario**, v. 19, n. 1, p. 76–91, 2023. DOI: 10.30972/nvt.1916712.

GARCIA, W. P.; PAN, M. A. G. D. S. Vivência Acadêmica, Formação Universitária, Desenvolvimento Humano: Contribuições De Vigotski Ao Ensino Superior. **Psicologia Escolar e Educacional**, v. 27, 2023. DOI: 10.1590/2175-35392023-248475.

GOMES, C.; REY, F. L. G. Inclusão escolar: representações compartilhadas de profissionais da educação acerca da inclusão escolar. **Psicologia: Ciência e Profissão**, v. 27, n. 3, p. 406–417. DOI: 10.1590/S1414-98932007000300004.

GONZÁLEZ REY, F. L. El lugar de las emociones en la constitución social de lo psíquico: El aporte de Vigotski. **Educación & Sociedad**, v. 21, 132-148, 2000.

GONZÁLEZ REY, F. Subjetividad social, sujeto y representaciones sociales. **Diversitas: Perspectivas en psicología**, v. 4, n. 2, p. 225-243, 2008. Available at:http://www.scielo.org.co/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1794-99982008000200002. Accessed in: 15 Jan. 2025.

GRANADO, J. I. F.; SANTOS, A. A. A.; ALMEIDA, L. S.; SOARES, A. P.; GUISANDE, M. A. Integração acadêmica de estudantes universitários: contributos para a adaptação e validação do QVA-r no Brasil. **Psicologia e Educação**, v. 4, n. 2, 2005.

GUANIN-FAJARDO, J. H.; CASILLAS BARRANQUERO, J. Contexto universitário, profesores y estudiantes: vínculos y éxito académico. **Revista Iberoamericana de Educación**, v. 88, n. 1, p. 127–146, 2022. DOI: 10.35362/rie8814733.

GUERONI, L.P.G.; POMPEO, D.A.; EID, L.P.; FERREIRA, JR. M.A.; SEQUEIRA, C.A.C.; LOURENÇÃO, L.G. Interventions for Strengthening General Self-Efficacy Beliefs in College Students: An Integrative Review. **Rev Bras Enferm.**, v. 77, n. 1. 2024. DOI: 10.1590/0034-7167-2023-0192.

GUZMÁN-UTRERAS, E.; BAEZA-UGARTE, C. G.; MORALES-NAVARRO, M. Vivencias académicas y salud mental en tres cohortes universitarias bajo emergencia covid-

19. **Revista Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales, Niñez y Juventud**, v. 21, n. 2, p. 50–71, 2023.

HAUGSBAKK, G. Edição especial: 30 anos de TIC e aprendizagem na educação – grandes mudanças e desafios. **Seminar.net**, v. 16, n. 2, 2020.

KRAMER, G. G. **Vínculos organizacionais**: um estudo de caso em uma organização pública. 2003. 143 f. Dissertação (Mestrado em Administração) – Universidade Federal do Paraná, Curitiba, 2003.

KRAMER, G. G.; FARIA, J. H. Vínculos organizacionais. **Revista de Administração Pública**, v. 41, n. 1, p. 83–104, 2007. Available at: <https://periodicos.fgv.br/rap/article/view/6881>. Accessed in: 15 Jan. 2025.

LACERDA, I. P.; YUNES, M. A. M.; VALENTINI, F. Permanência no ensino superior e a rede de apoio de estudantes residentes em moradia estudantil. **Internacional de Educação Superior**, Campinas, p. 1–18, 2022. DOI: 10.20396/riesup.v8i0.8663399.

LARROSA, J. A operação ensaio: sobre o ensaiar e o ensaiar-se no pensamento, na escrita e na vida. **Educação & Realidade**, Porto Alegre, v. 29, n. 1, p. 27–44, 2004.

LIMA, V.; MEIRA COSTA, A.; IENACO DE VASCONCELOS, M.; LOURENÇO, L. Saúde mental no ensino superior: revisão de literatura. **Interação em Psicologia**, v. 26, n. 3, 2023. DOI: 10.5380/riep.v26i3.76204.

LOK, Bee-Lan; CHENG, M. Y.; CHOONG, Chee-Keong. A relação entre o treinamento de habilidades soft e o desenvolvimento de recursos humanos e o desempenho organizacional. **International Journal of Business and Society**, Malásia, 2020.

MACHADO, L. V.; FACCI, M. G. D.; BARROCO, S. M. S. Teoria das emoções em Vigotski. **Psicologia Em Estudo**, v. 16, n. 4, p. 647–657, 2011. Available at: <https://www.scielo.br/j/pe/a/cvL9hMXKctvZpzF3nLFdyYw/?format=html&lang=pt>. Accessed in: 15 Jul. 2025.

MALEQUETA, A. F.; SANTOS, L. S.; PERY, M. R. M. Análise da satisfação acadêmica de estudantes do curso de Educação Física e Desporto do ensino a distância da UCM. **Educação a Distância**, v. 7, n. 1, p. 73–92, 2017.

MARTÍN-BARÓ, I. O papel do Psicólogo. **Estudos de Psicologia (natal)**, v. 2, n. 1, p. 7–27, 1997. DOI: 10.1590/S1413-294X1997000100002.

MEDEIROS, L. A.; GONÇALVES, P. da R. Jovens Universitários de Camadas Populares e suas Trajetórias Empreendedoras a partir da Vivência Acadêmica. **Arquivos do CMD**, v. 6, n. 2, p. 66-78, 2018. DOI: 10.26512/cmd.v6i2.22409.

MENG, Q.; ZHANG, Q. The influence of academic self-efficacy on university students' academic performance: the mediating effect of academic engagement. **Sustainability**, v. 15, p. 5767, 2023. DOI: 10.3390/su15075767.

MÉRIDA-LÓPEZ, S.; EXTREMERA, N.; QUINTANA-ORTS, C. Exigencias académicas en estudios de posgrado a distancia y sus vínculos con el agotamiento y la regulación de las

emoções próprias. **Revista Internacional de Pedagogia e Innovación Educativa**, v. 3, n. 1, p. 139–154, 2023.

MOREIRA, M. C. N. Trajectories and moral experiences of rare and chronic illness in biographies: a theoretical essay. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva**, v. 24, n. 10, p. 3651–3661, 2019. DOI: 10.1590/1413-812320182410.33532018.

NASCIMENTO, A. C. P. L.; FERRAZ, R. de C. S. N. Transtorno de personalidade borderline: narrativa de uma vivência acadêmica no ensino superior. **Revista de Estudos em Educação e Diversidade (REED)**, v. 2, n. 5, p. 1–15, 2021. DOI: 10.22481/reed.v2i5.9568.

NASCIMENTO, A. C. P. L.; FERRAZ, R. de C. S. N. Transtorno de personalidade borderline: narrativa de uma vivência acadêmica no ensino superior. **Revista de Estudos em Educação e Diversidade (REED)**, v. 2, n. 5, p. 1–15, 2021. DOI: 10.22481/reed.v2i5.9568.

NGUYEN, N.; LEBLANC, G. Corporate image and corporate reputation in customers' retention decisions in services. **Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services**, v. 8, p. 227–236, 2001. DOI: 10.1016/S0969-6989(00)00029-1.

NHANTUMBO, D. J.; CARREÑO, Á. B.; BRUCE-NHANTUMBO, B. S. Satisfação com a educação recebida e rendimento acadêmico em estudantes do ensino superior da cidade da Beira, Moçambique. **Revista Científica Electrónica de Educación y Comunicación en la Sociedad del Conocimiento**, v. 18, n. 2, p. 316-334, 2018. DOI: 10.30827/eticanet.v2i18.11894.

NINA, S. de F. M.; CRUZ DE OLIVEIRA, R. Vivências acadêmicas e sofrimento psíquico em estudantes de medicina. **Trabalho (En)Cena**, v. 4, n. 2, p. 451–464, 2019. DOI: 10.20873/2526-1487V4N2P451.

OLIVEIRA, E. S.; SILVÉRIO, C. E.; FLORES, R. P.; FELDKIRCHER, J. M.; NUNES, M. M.; OKUBO, R. Programa de extensão “Fisioterapia esportiva”: Uma vivência extensionista. **Revista Conexão UEPG**, v. 15, n. 3, p. 269-273, 2019.

OLIVEIRA, V. P.; MACIEL, L. F. P.; IAOCHITE, R. T.; SALLES, W. Das N.; NASCIMENTO, J. V.; FOLLE, A. Autoeficácia no ensino superior e satisfação com as experiências acadêmicas: percepções de estudantes de Educação Física. **Movimento**, v. 26, e26087, 2020.

ORGANIZAÇÃO MUNDIAL DA SAÚDE. **Informe mundial sobre salud mental**. Genebra, 2022.

PEREIRA, B. C. S.; GIL, C. Avaliando a satisfação dos alunos de escolas de administração: uma nova perspectiva de gestão. **Revista de Administração da UNIMEP**, v. 5, n. 1, 2007.

PEREIRA-NETO, L. L.; FARIA, A. A. G. B. T.; ALMEIDA, L. S. Adaptação e evidências de validação do Questionário de Satisfação com a Experiência Acadêmica Remota (QSEAR). **Revista Ibero-Americana de Estudos em Educação**, p. 2626–2647, 2022. DOI: 10.21723/riaee.v17i4.16756.

PERIS BLAT, I. Una lectura de los vínculos interesados. **Revista rita**, v. 11, p. 118-125. 2019.

QUEIROZ, T. P.; PAULA, C. P. A. A força do imaginário: apego, vínculo e identidade acadêmica como potencializadores da relação com egressos. **Prisma.com**, v. 34, p. 84–104, 2017.

RIBEIRO, M. R. F.; PONTES, V. M. A.; SILVA, E. A. A contribuição da extensão universitária na formação acadêmica: desafios e perspectivas. **Revista Conexão UEPG**, v. 13, n. 1, p. 52–65, 2017. DOI: 10.5212/Rev.Conexao.v.13.i1.0004.

RODRIGUES, C. S.; DO NASCIMENTO COSTA, P. H.; DA CUNHA GOMES, J. A.; ALBUQUERQUE, F. B. V.; PENHA, A. J. B. S.; DE ARAÚJO, W. F.; DA SILVA, M. A. M. Prática de enfermagem em saúde coletiva: Vivência acadêmica na atenção primária à saúde. **Revista Brasileira de Extensão Universitária**, v. 14, n. 3, p. 213-222, 2023.

ROQUE, Y. V.; DE LEÓN, R. S. G. P.; SUÁREZ, A. L.; DUANY, Z. S.; MONTERO, H. C. La formación académica en salud reflejada en los egresados de la ELAM y su vínculo con la teoría Educación Avanzada. **Panorama Cuba y Salud**, v. 13, n. S1, p. 318–321, 2018.

ROSO, A.; ROMANINI, M. Empoderamento individual, empoderamento comunitário e conscientização: um ensaio teórico. **Psicologia e Saber Social**, v. 3, n. 1, p. 83–95, 2014.

SANTOS, A. A. A.; ZANON, C.; ILHA, V. D. Autoeficácia na formação superior: seu papel preditivo na satisfação com a experiência acadêmica. **Estudos de Psicologia**, Campinas, v. 36, 2019. DOI: 10.1590/1982-0275201936e160077.

SANTOS, L. C.; SEVERO, L. R.; CORREIA, L. A. Desafios ao Engajamento Acadêmico no Ensino Superior: Uma Análise a Partir da Avaliação Discente. **Revista Internacional de Educação Superior**, Campinas, SP, 2022. Available at: <https://periodicos.sbu.unicamp.br/ojs/index.php/riesup/article/view/8666403>. Accessed in: 15 Jan. 205.

SANTOS, L. E. D.; SCHNEIDER, F. V. M.; FREITAG, V. L.; COLOMÉ, I. C. S. Vivências acadêmicas em programa de educação na rede de atenção a pessoas com deficiência. **Revista Brasileira em Promoção da Saúde**, v. 31, n. 2, 2018. DOI: 10.5020/18061230.2018.6865.

SANTOS, M. A. C.; ROMEIRO, V. A satisfação com a experiência acadêmica influencia a relação de confiança comportamental com a instituição?. **Revista Brasileira de Ensino Superior**, Passo Fundo, v. 3, n. 1. p. 78-97, 2017. DOI: 10.18256/2447-3944/rebes.v7n1p78-97.

SCHLEICH, A.; POLYDORO, S.; SANTOS, A. Escala de satisfação com a experiência acadêmica de estudantes do ensino superior. **Avaliação Psicológica**, v. 5, n. 1, p. 11-20, 2006. Available at: https://pepsic.bvsalud.org/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1677-04712006000100003. Accessed in: 15 Jan. 205.

SILVA, G.; NETO, I.; ROCHA, A.; MONTEIRO, L.; RAUBER, S. Relação entre autoestima e saúde mental de estudantes universitários: estudo transversal. **Psicologia, Saúde & Doenças**, v. 24, n. 1, p. 104–114, 2023. DOI: 10.15309/23psd240109.

SIQUEIRA, L. P.; PEREIRA, H. A. de L.; NASCIMENTO-JUNIOR, J. R. A. do; MACHADO, A. S.; MORAES, J. F. V. N. Perfil e nível de satisfação com as vivências

acadêmicas de graduandos do curso de Educação Física da UNIVASF. **Debates Em Educação**, v. 12, n. 28, p. 455–473, 2020. DOI: 10.28998/2175-6600.2020v12n28p455-473.

SÍVERES, L. Extensão Universitária: Processo de aprendizagem e procedimento de desenvolvimento sustentável. **CATAVENTOS-Revista de Extensão da Universidade de Cruz Alta**, v. 4, 2012.

SOARES, A. B.; LEME, V. B. R.; GOMES, G.; PENHA, A. P.; MAIA, F. A.; LIMA, C. A.; ARAÚJO, A. M. Expectativas acadêmicas de estudantes en los primeros años de enseñanza superior. **Arquivos Brasileiros de Psicologia**, v. 70, n. 1, p. 206-223, 2018.

SOARES, A. P.; VASCONCELOS, R.; ALMEIDA, L. S. **Adaptação e satisfação na Universidade**: Apresentação e validação do Questionário de Satisfação Acadêmica (QSA). 2002.

SUEHIRO, A. C. B.; ANDRADE, K. S. Satisfação com a experiência acadêmica: um estudo com universitários do primeiro ano. **Psicol. pesq.**, Juiz de Fora, v. 12, n. 2, p. 77-86, 2018. DOI: 10.24879/2018001200200147.

TASCHETTO, L. R.; ROSA, G. C. Mobilidade acadêmica internacional: caminhos para vínculos transculturais. **TEXTURA-Revista de Educação e Letras**, v. 21, n. 47, 2019.

TONTINI, G.; WALTER, S. A. Antecedentes da qualidade percebida de um curso de administração: uma abordagem não linear. **Revista Brasileira de Gestão de Negócios**, v. 13, n. 40, 2011. DOI: 10.7819/rbgn.v13i40.846.

TORRACO, R. J. Writing integrative reviews of the literature: Methods and purposes. **International Journal of Adult Vocational Education and Technology (IJAVET)**, v. 7, n. 3, p. 62-70, 2016. DOI: 10.4018/IJAVET.2016070106.

TREJO, R. G.; CHACÓN, G. M.; SUÁREZ, G.; ROJAS, M. F. Vínculos y diferencias entre la escritura académica y la escritura profesional en una carrera técnica universitaria. **Cuaderno de Pedagogía Universitaria**, v. 16, n. 32, p. 35–47, 2019. DOI: 10.29197/cpu.v16i32.344.

VALDIVIA, A. C. Vínculos en la universidad chilena: voces de docentes y académicos. **Revista Contemporânea de Educação**, v. 14, n. 29, p. 136-155. 2019.

VYGOTSKY, L. S. **A formação social da mente**. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 1989.

VYGOTSKY, L. S. **Pensamento e linguagem**. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 1995.

ZEEVALLOS, A. L.; WASHBURN, M. Criando uma Cultura de Sucesso do Aluno: O Programa de Mentoria de Pares SEEK Scholars. **Em prática**, Nova York: Wiley Online Library, 2014. DOI: 10.1590/1981-5271v45.supl.1-20210117.

CRediT Author Statement

- Acknowledgements:** Not applicable.
 - Funding:** National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq).
 - Conflicts of interest:** None declared.
 - Ethical approval:** Not required.
 - Data and material availability:** Information can be made available upon request.
 - Authors' contributions:** Fabiana Pinto de Almeida Bizarria: conceptualization, leadership, and primary development of the manuscript; Leonardo Victor de Sá Pinheiro: contribution to the development of the theoretical framework, data analysis, and discussion; Ana Cristine Mendes da Silva: data analysis and discussion; Flávia Lorene Sampaio Barbosa: overall manuscript review and contributions to analyses, discussions, and final considerations.
-

Processing and editing: Editora Ibero-Americana de Educação
Proofreading, formatting, standardization and translation

